

Methodologies, Technologies and Tools Enabling e-Government

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Juan Santos Gago

(Universidade de Vigo, Vigo, Spain
jsgago@det.uvigo.es)

Luis Anido Rifón

(Universidade de Vigo, Vigo, Spain
lanido@det.uvigo.es)

The seventh edition of the International Conference on Methodologies, Technologies and Tools enabling e-Government (MeTTeG) received a large number of submissions mainly from the European continent. The Program Committee responsible for the review process was comprised of a total of 20 programme committee members. The work of this group of highly qualified experts was outstanding and made it possible to gather high quality papers in different areas related to e-Government. This special issue of the Journal of Universal Computer Science includes the best two papers of the conference, which have been additionally reviewed and extended after the conference. Two additional papers were selected after an open call. Altogether, they represent a good overview of the current e-Government related research areas: recommender systems, e-Documents, Open Data and interoperability.

Juan Santos Gago and Luis Anido Rifón
Universidade de Vigo
Spain